

Paper 2

A Study on the Consequent Influences of COVID-19 Pandemic on Individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorder in India

Menezes Ida Sylvia 1*, KT Shwetha 2 ** & D'Mello Laveena 3***

*Research Scholar, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangalore, email: dishaasd2006@gmail.com, Orcid ID: 0000-0001-7654-9217

** Assistant Professor, School of Social Sciences & Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. Email: kt.shwetha@gmail.com
Orcid ID: 0000-0003-0895-6333

*** Associate Professor, School of Social Sciences & Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka, India. Email: lavyonoronha@gmail.com,
Orcid ID: 0000-003-1935002X

Corresponding Author Contact number- +918073687619

ABSTRACT

Purpose: *In the exceptional disruption and social isolation of the COVID-19 pandemic, households round the arena are confronted with questions of ways their youngsters can thrive in those conditions. The ever-present demanding situations for kids with unique fitness needs such as autism spectrum disorder (ASD), the disaster relay particular problems due to terrible influences of the COVID-19 pandemic.*

Methodology: *A cross sectional study of 30 families of children with ASD has been conducted during the second wave of the pandemic. Parents have been asked to fill out self-report questionnaire through google form.*

Findings: *Researcher has made an attempt to understand the vulnerability of ASD individuals, the challenges encountered and the stressors. The role of the healthcare facilities during the pandemic like COVID -19, the measures taken to ease the burden of ASD community has been studied. The benefit of online services and telehealth during pandemic along with its significance and positive benefits has been identified. The future need of similar services in combating pandemics and the strategies to make maximum benefit of such distance services has been learned.*

Originality: *The efforts to prioritise the need of the vulnerable community and their responsibilities in reintegrating them into the society with risk measures have been weighed. The impact on the overall growth and development and on the psychological realm of ASD individuals has been identified with its outcome and the management. What best can be offered and done during relevant crisis and what measures need to be taken has been deeply observed.*

Paper type: *Research Qualitative Case study type*

Keywords: *COVID-19 pandemic, autism spectrum disorder, vulnerability, challenges, stressors, online services, social isolation.*

1.INTRODUCTION

The unexpected emergence of a novel coronavirus (COVID-19) has created uncertainty in all parts of society, causing widespread worry, anxiety, and stress. The unexpected epidemic presented obstacles in dealing with quick changes, forcing fitness to adapt in order to survive. When we look at the pandemic history of any infectious disease, we can see how important it is to protect the psychological and behavioural domains, since they are among the most vulnerable owing to negative consequences. The frontline stressors are inescapable mental stress and worry, sleep difficulties, and insecurity owing to the pandemic's harmful impact. The terror of an unknown end will intensify. The worry of an unknown end will exacerbate the negative consequences already present, creating the

question of how long will it last? Most significantly, the infection's bar graph pattern induced horrified fear in people, stopping them from going about their daily lives normally. The spread of sickness appeared to afflict all members of the family in due time, with children being the most affected due to their naïve understanding. As we proceeded with the delta plus variety, the lucky flavour of children's safety in consideration with COVID-19 has decreased, and the burden of being infectious with vulnerability has increased. In comparison to the general population, people with autism spectrum disorders suffer from excessive anxiety due to a lack of understanding of the pandemic notion and difficulties deciphering the myth that hides the truth [2]. The pervasiveness of the pandemic, as well as the disruptions in upcoming events, upsets the organised routine, causing chaos and tension in the general populace, exacerbated by the unpredictability of the situation. Because of the difficulty in adapting to new occurrences owing to their unpredictability and life changes, living in the autism community is more difficult.

2. INCREASED VULNERABILITY AND AUTISM

Vulnerability is defined as an individual's or a population's inability to forecast, adapt, tolerate, and recover from catastrophic outcomes [3]. As families all around the world struggle to figure out how to best help their children, a critical issue arises: how to support children with autism, who are cognitively impaired and incapable of understanding or comprehending the world around them. Pandemic has been a difficulty for autistic children who are already challenged [4]. The most difficult task is introducing COVID's entire outline! Because abstract concepts are restricted in the brains of these small children, reducing disruptive behaviours requires a highly challenging task that no one would dare to undertake. The panic surrounding the spread of the disease, the deadly outcome of COVID, the consequences of not wearing the mask, or the need for social distancing are all highly challenging tasks that no one would dare to undertake. Their cognitive executive functions and intellectual levels limit their ability to understand and act on COVID-19 infection alerts [5]. In the mind of the researcher, an overpowering question arises: what is more vulnerable? In the life of autism, is it the outcome of the pandemic or the outcome of the pandemic procedures in their prevention? When it comes to disease conditions, the diagnosis of autism is the vulnerability in the life of an autistic child. Due to the limits established in accordance with pandemic prevention, the added vulnerability of pandemic bad consequences makes it more vulnerable. Autism children's lives are exceptional when they are free of their daily routines. The severity of the illness, as expressed by the child on the spectrum, disrupts the laid basis of behavioural, educational, vocational, and racial norms. The steps to be made to combat the pandemic's deterrents in the wellbeing of these neuro-developmentally challenged youngsters are a top priority for parents and healthcare providers. When we excuse the characteristics of autism, the core feature of this heavily labelled diagnosis is the social communication and the functional language challenges. Diagnosed children with autism, under therapeutic interventions as they just initiating to communicate, the unpredicted pandemic strategies of lockdown and closure of all therapy centres and social gatherings at the right time devouring the buds of speech and language as they just erupt! This is one of the major adverse effects further complicated by wearing masks. Further confusing the distorted signals of communication in the brain, blocking them by wearing masks during socialization. What irony of these kids at the time of learning to pronounce or to repeat a word or sentence!! Considering this single outcome in acquisition of language in the life of autism child, we can imagine or concretely calculate the outcome of disruptive behaviours and the cognitive skill developments, the comprehensive and intellectual skills as well as the attention increment or focus.

3. COMMON CHALLENGES

3.1 Anxiety

What makes an individual with ASD to be more affected in his mental health? As discussed above the chore characteristics of autism affecting its behavioural component significantly due to inability to communicate or comprehend the built-up emotions bring about more aggression, disruptive behaviours in simple words as tantrums and the refusal or avoidance of engaging in any daily engagements. The only way to handle these behaviours and to get normalcy in these kids is to engage them in physical activities and routines to drain the tempo to reduce hyperactivity. Studies have shown that individuals with autism face sensory impairments or sensory sensitivities [7]. The sensitivities may be over responsiveness or under responsive to various stimuli as each autism has uniqueness. The compulsion on the usage of mask adds to the existing irritability due to sensory issues making it impossible to rationalize it. Children with over sensitivities find it too difficult to wear a mask as the tags and even the elastic ties too sensitive and are impossible to bear with. Inconsideration to five major sensory organs and the stimulations, the food sensitivity is also one of the major issues which indulge in the health component; interference of which leads to poor health. Personal aversions towards the food and the picky eating habits exacerbates the situation during pandemic due to unavailability of the supply of the demanding items as well as the shutdown of the major stores. These could be some of the possibilities why autism population has higher risk of poor health in comparison to normal population [8].

3.2 Dealing with change

In conditions such as developmental disabilities, the whole concept of progressive damages that takes place during the developmental stages anchor the mental health of the individuals challenging them to adapt, acute stress related situations such as post traumatic or covid 19 pandemics as present scenarios[9]. Giving rise to acute psychotic or mood disorders with suicidal ideation or tendencies, due to anticipated fear of loss of loved ones and trouble adapting[10]. The pervasive developmental disordered people have increased vulnerability to mental health disorders than to the typical population[11]. The unknown end of covid 19 pandemic as well as the co-occurring complexities such as emotional disorders decay the resilience [12]. The comorbidity with autism complicates the skills required for adaptation, learning as well as a healthy life style. Children with intellectual disabilities and physical disabilities struggle in executive functioning skills as well as ambulatory skills respectively. [13]

3. METHODOLOGY

This study proposes a cross-sectional exploratory survey design by recruiting purposive sample of 30 individuals with autism spectrum disorder in India. Qualitative research by collecting raw data from purposive sampling, was applied. In depth information through thematic content analysis, carried out, as qualitative research. To study the association of unexpected outbreak of COVID 19 pandemic and its effect on the vulnerable ASD individuals. The analysis of the study helps to identify the constraints of strategies applied due to COVID19, approaches used and its impact on the ASD individuals, in handling the post pandemic situation. Through narrative interviews accepting the new normal post pandemic, the management of stress, its effect on the mental health was analysed. Readiness for major life transitions in near future were explored in various domains by in depth interviews. Autism individuals' behaviour and adjustment of the family members to the pandemic situation was analysed.

The objectives of the study are;

- (i) To study the vulnerability of autism children;
- (ii) To study the impact due to mitigation strategies of COVID-19;
- (iii) To study the common challenges to deal with the changes;

4.ANALYSIS

4.1 Transition Planning

The unpredicted mitigation strategies to battle COVID -19 considerably affected the families of autism. The stay-at-home remedies and social distancing handicapped the individuals with autism drastically as compared with other disabilities. Children and the adults with ASD struggle the most due to in situ learning interruption as the generalization of the task and skills serves the best in autism children. The practical teaching and learning methods as best taught in the environment that best suits the goals to be achieved were shuttered due to the lock down restrictions and social distancing. These individuals had to learn basic skills, community skills, the educational and the vocational skills under one roof with limited resources.[14]. Applied behaviour therapy (ABA) serves best in understanding the cause of any challenging behaviours, its attention seeking or escapism. All the encouraging behaviours need to be reinforced positively and disruptive actions reinforced through negative reinforcement such as time out or withdrawing the stimulus.As we understand the core features of autism or ASD is the social communication, the stay-at-home strategies have completely locked the lifestyle and learning in autism individual. Naturalistic interventions through social communication intervened due to social distancing protocols. And wearing masks further closes the mouth of a minimal communicating person making it impossible to initiate any communication. These logistical barriers in the journey of ABA therapies and the autism individual further challenges integrated therapies such as speech and language and or the occupational. The small classroom settings best applied in the immediate care of the autism child as the one -to- one attention therapy faded, traversing them into the main stream. Closure of the therapy centres or the small integrated classroom environments could not even carry on at home settings due to social distancing [15].

4.2Horizontal Planning

Does education really matter in children with autism? Here the age group specification favours the outcome of teaching or learning at the early age. As we always say and advice as well as witness the early intervention intrusions and its fruitful outcome. The plasticity of brain intensifies due to persistent interventions, making it possible to learn if started right on time. And that is the reason of concern why education need to be given an utmost importance in the life of autism? The shutdown of all educational institutions in the beginning of covid pandemic to mitigate the spread of infection panicked many families both typically developing as well as with disabilities. As there was no room for any planning or developing modalities to fit in distance learning. It was

highly challenging to adapt to the new curriculum that could fit in for any population in the society. The challenge was admirable when complex communication needs to be met and the curriculum to be developed for various disabilities including ASD due to its uniqueness. As the pandemic paved the way to adapt the new life style, the educational services with its limited resources emerged and distance learning played an important role in the field of education [16]. Effective use of delivering reinforcements, controlling the distractions and navigating the tantrums is rather herculean. Adaptation to new learning is quite challenging even in the life of parents depending on the age with other demands.

4.3 Vertical Planning

Irrespective of the age group individual affected with autism as pervasive developmental disorder face significant challenges including vocational. Adults with ASD face loss of community services due to the pandemic [17]. With the essence of social isolation due to social communication disorder the adult autism individual face greater potential risk than the typical adults. They isolate themselves from the social gatherings and community activities. It is well understood that due to their disability they are less employed and restricted with their participation in employment-oriented tasks [18]. They have unique life style, well-structured and organized, requiring attention and accompaniment for the security and transport reason, when employment concerned. Sudden changes in their schedules due to stay-at-home and lock downs they face adjustment problems to the newly provoked situation which is unstructured and time oriented. The risk of contamination required maximum health guidelines to combat covid as well as challenged social isolation [19]. Adaptation is part and parcel of every human being and we usually adapt sooner or later subjected to the degree of adjustments. But in the life of autism, this is rather unpredictable as the disorder itself cumbersome. The rigidity with adaptation in autism critically damages the mental hygiene, and rescheduling with readaptation with the fear of temporary fallback, makes no sense in these individuals with cognitive skills deficits. Though gradual reintroduction to social environment is the criteria for a better adjustment, regression of skills once mastered were challengeable due to lack of practice for months together as well as the fine-gross motor co-ordinations.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Accepting the New Normal

Stay-at-home protocols though served as miracle cure for corona spread, social-emotional trauma could never be replaced to the community of autism. Though the typical population underwent considerable damage in these domains, the ASD families due to the functional fixedness and the inability to make use of the available in-situ resources suffered the most. The digital world extremely met the fun and entertainment fields to the general population on the other hand. Which hardly made any difference to the autism community. The uncertainties and unpredictable changes created chaos in planning educational and recreational programs affecting the future preparation. Re-engagement with peer group and companionship of same peers is highly challenging giving rise to strangers' anxiety as well as accommodation confront. The dilemma of re-engagement to the routines and the return to quarantines as the corona wave spikes, continuous adjustment to uncertainties is stressful to individuals with cognitive dysfunction. The ultimate outcome of temper tantrums leading to exacerbate behaviour due to unpredictable environment. The brief transition to the existing condition or the unprecedented dark future, is the worry of many parents as they are confused about how to proceed!

5.2 Readiness for Major Life Transitions

Telehealth and online flat forms have shown remarkable outcome in assisting individuals to accept the new environment, to adjust and to adapt new normal, and to reintegrate in the community. This might traverse creative solutions towards resilience and preparedness in near future. Emergency preparedness for optimizing coping, guidance and resilience will be crucial for intervention and mental health hygiene [20]. Though the emergence of digitalization and the online services were in practice in various healthcare sections, before pandemic, the mental health had restrictions due to the direct clinical observation and its findings to apply on regular basis [21]. Pandemic made it practically possible to avail as the best alternative including vulnerable groups with ASD. It is the best medium of practice for people with limited resources trying to reach the efficient behavioural health professionals through technology. Interstate and international opinions and differential diagnosis always remained incomplete as people have no resources to reach the best, pandemic has strengthened the connectivity and collaboration to individuals in need and made it possible.

6. CONCLUSION

The question of significance of vulnerability arises in autism spectrum disorder community with regard to any pandemic including the Covid-19, as they have social interaction and functional language limitations. The pandemic

worsens the characteristics due to prolonging social isolation. What best could be offered to these individuals with ASD is the concern and how suitably could we make it possible without further deteriorating the tag of vulnerability! Prioritising the reintegration to these groups ensures reduction in post pandemic impact. Social environments such as schools can be converted into intervention and training centres during this type of pandemics to accommodate ASD individuals following strictly the social distance and curfews. Collaboration with local community leaders in instrumenting the crisis in ASD families and providing such environment for the upliftment of ASD individuals. COVID-19 has made to realise the extent of preparedness measures during similar crisis for productive and effective skills management. Potentials to strengthen these services at local level, to meet the unique needs in the future. Critical innovations including the individual with ASD in the process when applicable, to prepare measures will empower solely. Online resources have made remarkable contribution in problem solving skills of ASD communities, hence the availability of electronic equipment's to the unaffordable families would be utmost important to provide structured supportive programs.

REFERENCES

- [1] Cox DJ, Plavnick JB, Brodhead MT. 2020A Proposed Process for Risk Mitigation During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Behaviour Analysis in Practice*, 13(2), 1-7.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [2] Van Steensel, F. J., Bögels, S. M., & Perrin, S. (2011). Anxiety disorders in children and adolescents with autistic spectrum disorders: A meta-analysis. *Clinical child and Family Psychology Review*, 14(3), 302.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [3] World Health Organization. (2002). The world health report 2002: Reducing risks, promoting healthy life. *World Health Organization*.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [4] Den Houting J. (2020). Stepping Out of Isolation: Autistic People and COVID-19. *Autism in Adulthood*. *Published ahead of print*, 2(2).
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [5] Courtenay, K.; Perera, B. (2020). COVID-19 and people with intellectual disability: Impacts of a pandemic. *Irish Journal of Psychological Medicine*, 37, 231–236.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [6] Rydzewska E, Hughes-McCormack LA, Gillberg C, Henderson A, MacIntyre C, Rintoul J, et al. (2019) Prevalence of sensory impairments, physical and intellectual disabilities, and mental health in children and young people with self/proxy-reported autism: Observational study of a whole country population. *Autism Journal*, 23(5), 1201-1209.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [7] Dunn, K., Rydzewska, E., Macintyre, C., Rintoul, J., & Cooper, S. A. (2019). The prevalence and general health status of people with intellectual disabilities and autism co-occurring together: A total population study. *Journal of Intellectual Disability Research*, 63(4), 277–285.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [8] Liu, N., Zhang, F., Wei, C., Jia, Y., Shang, Z., Sun, L., et al. (2020). Prevalence and predictors of PTSS during COVID-19 outbreak in China hardest-hit areas: Gender differences matter. *Journal of Psychiatry Research*, 287, 112921.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [9] Ammerman, B. A., Burke, T. A., Jacobucci, R., & McClure, K. (2020). Preliminary investigation of the association between COVID-19 and suicidal thoughts and behaviours in the US. *Journal of Psychiatric Research*, 134, 32-38.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [10] Diaz, A. D., & Baweja, R. (2021). The role of neurotropism in psychiatric patients with COVID-19. *European Archives of Psychiatry and Clinical Neuroscience*, 271, 385–386.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [11] Wallace, G. L., Kenworthy, L., Pugliese, C. E., Popal, H. S., White, E. I., Brodsky, E., et al. (2016). Real-world executive functions in adults with autism spectrum disorder: Profiles of impairment and associations with adaptive functioning and co-morbid anxiety and depression. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 46(3), 1071–1083.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [12] Narzisi, A. (2020). Phase 2 and later of COVID-19 lockdown: Is it possible to perform remote diagnosis and intervention for autism spectrum disorder? An online-mediated approach. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 9(6), 1850.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)

- [13] Dotson, W. H., Leaf, J. B., Sheldon, J. B., & Sherman, J. A. (2010). Group teaching of conversational skills to adolescents on the autism spectrum. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders*, 4(2), 199–209.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [14] Eshraghi, A. A., Li, C., Alessandri, M., Messinger, D. S., Eshraghi, R. S., Mittal, R., & Armstrong, F. D. (2020). COVID-19: Overcoming the challenges faced by individuals with autism and their families. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 7(5), 481–483.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [15] Hess KL, Morrier MJ, Heflin LJ, et al(2008). Autism treatment survey: Services received by children with autism spectrum disorders in public school classrooms. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorder*, 38, 961–971.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [16] Narzisi, A., (2020). Handle the Autism Spectrum Condition During Coronavirus (COVID-19) Stay at Home period: Ten Tips for Helping Parents and Caregivers of Young Children. *Brain Science*,10(4), 207.
[Google Scholar](#)
- [17] Eshraghi, A. A., Li, C., Alessandri, M., Messinger, D. S., Eshraghi, R. S., Mittal, R., & Armstrong, F. D. (2020). COVID-19: Overcoming the challenges faced by individuals with autism and their families. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 7(5), 481–483.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [18] Giallonardo, V., Sampogna, G., Del Vecchio, V., Luciano, M., Albert, U., Carmassi, C., et al. (2020). The impact of quarantine and physical distancing following COVID-19 on mental health: Study protocol of a multicentric Italian population trial. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 11, 533.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [19] Giallonardo, V., Sampogna, G., Del Vecchio, V., Luciano, M., Albert, U., Carmassi, C., et al. (2020). The impact of quarantine and physical distancing following COVID-19 on mental health: Study protocol of a multicentric Italian population trial. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 11, 533.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [20] Torous, J., & Wykes, T. (2020). Opportunities from the coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic for transforming psychiatric care with telehealth. *JAMA Psychiatry*;77(12):1205-1206.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
- [21] Myers, K. M., Valentine, J. M., & Melzer, S. M. (2008). Child and adolescent telepsychiatry: Utilization and satisfaction. *Telemedicine and e-Health*, 14(2), 131–137.
[Google Scholar](#) [CrossRef](#)
